

Synthesis and Absorption Spectra of Heterocyclic Quinonoid Chromophoric System : Pyrrocoline Quinones

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Manuscript received 3 June 1980, revised 19 March 1981, accepted 15 July 1981

A series of substituted pyrrocoline quinones has been synthesised. Their structure has been ascertained through elemental analysis, colour reaction and spectral data.

ALTHOUGH the chemistry of pyrrocoline and its derivatives has been widely studied¹ little is known about the spectra of these compounds². Pyrrocolines have been reported to be pharmacologically active³ against convulsions, motor and respiratory paralysis. These pyrrocoline ring systems are of interest as they serve as starting material in the synthesis of corresponding meso-dimethyl derivatives which are related to carcinogenic hydrocarbons.

Tilak *et al*⁴ reported the synthesis of a number of 5,7-disubstituted and 5,11-disubstituted pyrrocoline quinones obtained by the condensation of chloranil with active methylene compounds in presence of pyridine. However, no spectral study of these type of compounds has been made so far which has a bearing on their finer structure.

Some new isomeric bispyrrocoline quinones have been prepared by using quaternary β -ketoalkylpyridinium iodides. In these quaternary β -ketoalkylpyridinium iodides, an active methylene group is situated between a carbonyl group and a strongly electronegative quaternary nitrogen.

The following new products were obtained by this procedure : (1) 5,7-disubstituted benzo(1,2-b,4,5-b')-bispyrrocoline-6,12-quinone (E-form) and 5,11-disubstituted benzo(1,2-b,5,4-b')-bispyrrocoline-6,12-quinone (Z-form) (when pyridine is used) ; (2) 7,15-disubstituted benzo(1,2-b,4,5-b')-dibenz-(f,f')-bispyrrocoline-8,16-quinone (E-form) (when isoquinoline is used) ; and (3) 7,15-disubstituted benzo(1,2-b,4,5-b')-dibenz (h, h')-bispyrrocoline-8,16-quinone (E-form) (when quinoline is used).

In the case of (2) and (3) only *trans* form is obtained. It gives a brilliant blue to violet color in conc. H_2SO_4 ⁵. This indicates that the product should have the *trans* configuration which is the only product isolated. The formation of *cis* structure seems to be sterically hindered. (Z referring to the *meta* relationship of the two N atoms as opposed to *para* in the E isomer). Both these isomers contained nitrogen and possess the quinonoid moiety in them.

Experimental

All the reagents were thoroughly dried and purified before use. Melting points were determined on a Kofler instrument and are uncorrected. UV absorption spectra were recorded on a Beckman Spectrophotometer Model DU-2, using 1 cm path length quartz cells. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 677 Spectrophotometer in KBr. The purity of the compounds were checked by tlc, which gave a single spot.

Quaternary β -ketoalkyl iodides : The compounds were prepared by known methods⁷.

Disubstituted benzo-bispyrrocoline quinones : A mixture of chloranil (0.01 mole), quaternary β -ketoalkyl pyridinium iodide (0.01 mole) and pyridine (0.01 mole) in 25-30 ml ethanol was refluxed on a water bath for 4 hrs. when all the chloranil dissolved and a deep red coloured reaction mixture obtained. The product separating on cooling was filtered and washed with ethanol, ether, hot water and dried. It was chromatographed over alumina to separate the E-form from the Z-form of the compound. The E-form was recrystallised from benzene while the Z-form was recrystallised from ethanol. The details of eluants used, separation of bands, yields, m.p. etc. are given in Table 1.

Disubstituted benzo-dibenz (f, f')-pyrrocoline quinones : Same procedure was adopted. Only isoquinoline was used instead of pyridine. The product was recrystallised twice from pyridine. The yields, m.p. etc. are given in Table 2.

TABLE 1—DISUBSTITUTED BENZO-BISPYRROCOLINE QUINONES

Compound No.	R	Mol. formula	Form of compound	Colour test	Bands on column	m.p. °C	Eluants	Yield %	% Analysis		UV Spectra			
									Calcd.	Found	Ethanol	log ε		
											λ _{max} nm			
1.	COC ₂ H ₅	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₄	E	Bluish violet	Pinkish violet	327	Benzene	27	C, 72.3	72.1	347	4.20		
										H, 4.5	3.9	360	4.31	
			Z	Green	Green	298	Methanol : chloroform (80 : 20)	35	C, 72.3	71.9	338	4.34		
										H, 4.5	4.1	365	4.21	
2.	COC ₂ H ₇	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₄	E	Violet	Violet	322	Benzene : chloroform (40 : 60)	38	C, 73.0	72.7	340	4.15		
										H, 5.1	4.9	367	4.25	
			Z	Green	Yellowish green	287	Chloroform	22	C, 73.0	72.6	335	4.23		
										H, 5.1	4.7	373	4.17	
3.	COC ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	C ₃₄ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₆	E	Reddish violet	Reddish violet	>330	Benzene	45	C, 73.6	73.3	350	4.21		
										H, 3.9	3.1	357	4.27	
			Z	Olive green	Green	>330	Chloroform : Dioxane (60 : 40)	37	C, 73.6	73.1	333	4.15		
										H, 3.9	3.6	370	4.10	
4.	COC ₆ H ₄ O ₂ H ₂	C ₃₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₆	E	Blue	Bluish violet	>330	Benzene	19	C, 68.8	68.6	354	4.17		
										H, 3.2	2.8	371	4.27	
			Z	Green	Green	>330	Chloroform	27	C, 68.8	68.4	345	4.30		
										H, 3.2	3.0	367	4.20	
5.	COCH ₃	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄	E	Blue	Reddish violet	356	Benzene	22	C, 71.3	71.2	351	4.34		
										H, 3.7	3.4	382	4.22	
			Z	Olive green	Orange green	360	Methanol : Benzene (40 : 60)	17	C, 71.3	71.1	340	4.27		
										H, 3.7	3.5	362	4.15	
											N, 7.5	7.4	477	3.91

TABLE 2 7,15-DISUBSTITUTED BENZO(1,2-b, 4,5-b')-DIBENZ(f,f')PYRROCOLINE QUINONES

Compound No.	R	Mol. formula	Form of compound	Colour test	m.p. °C	Yield %	% Analysis		UV Spectra		
							Calcd.	Found	Ethanol	log ε	
										λ _{max} nm	
1.	COC ₂ H ₅	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₄	E	Blue	357	42	C, 76.4	76.1	352	4.19	
							H, 4.3	3.9	471	3.07	
							N, 5.5	5.1	545	4.34	
2.	COC ₂ H ₇	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₄	E	Blue	>360	27	C, 76.9	76.4	347	4.22	
							H, 4.9	4.6	463	3.13	
							N, 5.2	5.0	550	4.25	
3.	COC ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	C ₃₄ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₆	E	Bluish violet	337	34	C, 77.6	77.1	357	4.35	
							H, 3.9	3.5	448	3.27	
							N, 4.2	3.9	535	4.15	
4.	COC ₆ H ₄ O ₂ H ₂	C ₃₄ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₆	E	Blue	351	21	C, 72.9	72.3	351	4.23	
							H, 3.3	2.9	455	3.21	
							N, 4.2	3.9	531	4.10	

TABLE 3 7,15-DISUBSTITUTED-BENZO(1,2-b, 4,5-b')-DIBENZ(h,h')PYRROCOLINE QUINONES(I)

Compound No.	R	Mol. formula	Form of compound	Colour test	m.p. °C	Yield %	% Analysis		UV Spectra		
							Calcd.	Found	Ethanol	log ε	
										λ _{max} nm	
1.	COC ₂ H ₅	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₄	E	Bluish violet	347	47	C, 76.4	76.0	365	4.31	
							H, 4.3	4.1	477	3.73	
							N, 5.5	5.1	548	4.15	
2.	COC ₂ H ₇	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₄	E	Blue	355	50	C, 76.8	76.5	361	4.27	
							H, 4.9	4.6	470	3.77	
							N, 5.2	5.0	552	4.30	
3.	COC ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	C ₃₄ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₆	E	Blue	321	35	C, 77.6	77.2	369	4.30	
							H, 3.9	3.7	455	3.65	
							N, 4.2	4.0	540	4.17	
4.	COC ₆ H ₄ O ₂ H ₂	C ₃₄ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₆	E	Blue	>360	32	C, 72.9	72.2	360	4.31	
							H, 3.3	3.0	462	3.70	
							N, 4.2	3.7	535	4.15	

Disubstituted benzo-dibenz(h, h')-pyrrocoline quinones : In this case quaternary β -ketoalkyl quinolinium iodide and quinoline was used and the same procedure was adopted. The product was recrystallised twice from pyridine. The yields, m.p. etc. are given in Table 3.

Results and Discussion

The gross structure of these compounds has been determined on the basis of elemental analysis, colour reaction⁵ and spectral data. IR spectrum showed the following bands : 1670 (quinone carbonyl), 1315 (C-N) and 1505 cm^{-1} (aromatic ring).

The E-form gave blue to violet coloured solution in conc. H_2SO_4 . The Z-form gave green coloured solution in conc. H_2SO_4 . The pyrrocoline-quinones had the properties of substituted pyrrocolines. The base did not dissolve in cold dilute acid but did so when warmed and neither cooling nor dilution precipitated it.

The absorption spectra of *trans* and *cis* forms were quite distinct and each compound showed absorption at longer wavelengths with large extinction values than the corresponding *cis*-isomers e.g., the Stilbenes⁶.

Reaction mechanism :

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Prof. R. C. Kapoor, Head of Chemistry Department for providing laboratory facilities and to the U. G. C., New Delhi for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship to (R. P. S.). We are also thankful to the Director, C. D. R. I., Lucknow for the elemental analysis, ir spectra and to the referee for helpful suggestions in the reaction mechanism.

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